

ON THE PHOTOCHEMICAL DECOMPOSITION OF PLATINUM COMPLEXES. PART I. PHOTOCHEMICAL DECOMPOSITION OF THE PLATINUM COMPLEXES WITH OXALIC ACID AND MALONIC ACID

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The photochemical decomposition of platinum complexes with oxalic and malonic acids has been studied. With malonic acid it was found that when the ratio, potassium malonate/chloroplatinic acid, was slightly greater than 3, the quantum efficiency jumped to a higher value and an induction period appeared, intensity of absorbed radiation remaining constant. 50% reduced Pt-complexes, reduced in *d*- or *l*-circularly polarised light, showed no optical activity.

The action of light upon the complex salts has been studied from the standpoint of Stark-Einstein law. The theory of optical activity by van't Hoff and the demonstration of Werner that some complex salts may exist in optically active forms have lent interest to the study of the photochemical properties of these compounds. Interesting possibilities centre round the action of polarised light, especially circularly polarised light, on complex compounds containing Pt *i.e.*, chelates containing tetravalent metallic ion. Investigations on the photochemical reaction kinetics of these complex compounds are likely to throw some light on the stability of such compounds and of the rings of dibasic organic acids and metallic ions in chelate compounds. The present investigation was thus undertaken with these objects in view.

EXPERIMENTAL

The experimental arrangement and the method of measuring the intensity of radiation actually absorbed are the same as described by Banerjee (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 14, 61), and that for producing *d*- or *l*-circularly polarised light ($366 \mu\mu$) by Ghosh, Banerjee and Mukherjee (*ibid.*, p. 500). Kahlbaum's pure chloroplatinic acid of the formula $H_2PtCl_6 \cdot 6H_2O$ was used. Schott and Gen ultraviolet filter No. 312 and Zeiss monochromats were used for isolating the regions $366 \mu\mu$ and $436 \mu\mu$ respectively. The amount of chloroplatinic acid present was determined iodometrically. There was no dark reaction in 10 hours.

It is evident from Table I that with the blue light the reactions follow the unimolecular law. But in the ultraviolet the unimolecular velocity constants obtained decrease slightly with time. Hence in the latter case the velocity constant and also the quantum efficiency (γ) have been calculated for one hour (after the termination of the induction period).

The velocity of reaction (Table II) is independent of the concentration of potassium bioxalate, even when the ratio reductant/oxidant changes from 10 to 3.

The apparent increase of velocity constant with increase in the concentration of chloroplatinic acid (Table III) is due to the corresponding increase in the amount of absorbed radiation ($P/Q_1 = \text{constant}$).

The ratio P/Q shows that the velocity of reaction varies directly as the intensity of absorbed radiation (Table IV).

d- and *l*-Circularly polarised lights were found to be practically equally efficient. In our experiments in the ultraviolet light, it has been observed that the unimolecular velocity constant decreases with time. So it was thought undesirable to attach any importance to the value of the unimolecular velocity constants obtained with *d*- or *l*-circularly polarised light when the

Photochemical Decomposition of Complexes formed by Chloroplatinic Acid and Bioxalate of Potassium.

TABLE I

Determination of the order of reaction.

Chloroplatinic acid = 0.01M. Potassium oxalate = 0.12M. Temp. = 26°. $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ soln. = 0.0125M. λ = the wave-length of incident light. k_1 = velocity constant.

λ .	Time.	$\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ soln. *	k_1 .
366 $\mu\mu$	0 min.	1.7 c.c.	1.8×10^{-3}
	60	1.6	1.6
	120	1.51	1.4
	180	1.44	1.2
	240	1.38	
436	0	1.5	Induction period.
	120	1.11	5.43
	240	0.75	5.41
	360	0.51	5.42
	480	0.33	

* $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ solution equivalent to 1 c.c. of the reaction mixture.

TABLE II

Effect of varying concentration of potassium oxalate.

Chloroplatinic acid = 0.01M. R = conc. of reductant/conc. of oxidant.

λ .	Conc. of K-bioxalate.	Intensity abs. (in Einstein).	R.	k_1 .
436 $\mu\mu$	0.105M	9.36×10^{-10}	10.5	3.83×10^{-3}
	0.06	9.38	6	3.85
	0.03	9.37	3	3.84
366	0.105	4.1	10.5	5.11
	0.06	4.3	6	5.12
	0.03	4.2	3	5.13

TABLE III

Effect of varying the concentration of chloroplatinic acid

λ .	K-bioxalate	Chloroplatinic acid	I_{abs} .	k_1 .	P/Q .
436 $\mu\mu$	0.07M	0.0133M	11.4×10^{-10}	5×10^{-3}	0.43
	0.05	0.006	8.55	3.83	0.44
366	0.07	0.0133	2.13	2.7	1.27
	0.05	0.006	1.50	1.9	1.26

TABLE V

Determination of quantum efficiency (γ)

λ .	K-bioxalate	Platinic acid.	I_{abs} .	γ .
366 $\mu\mu$	0.105M	0.01M	1347 ergs.	0.84
436	0.105	0.01	684	0.73

TABLE IV

Effect of varying the intensity of absorbed radiation

Chloroplatinic acid = 0.01M. K-bioxalate = 0.07M.

	436 $\mu\mu$	366 $\mu\mu$.
$I_{\text{abs}} \cdot 10^{10}$	13.84	7.05
$k_1 \times 10^3$	5.75	3.22
P/Q	0.41	0.44
		1.22
		1.26

TABLE VI

Extinction coefficient of Pt complexes and reduced Pt complexes.

	Mol. extinction coefficient (ϵ) in.	
	366 $\mu\mu$.	436 $\mu\mu$.
Pt (ic) complex	31	20
Pt (ous) complex	10	16

solution had to be exposed to light for sufficiently long period to get an appreciable amount of reaction. The 50% reduced Pt-complex solution was however examined for any optical activity by exposure to *d*- or *l*-circularly polarised light, but was found to possess none.

The mol. extinction coefficient (Table VI) has been measured by the well known formula $c. d = \log I_0/I_t$, the terms having the usual significance.

The mechanism of the photochemical process can be put thus—

- (i) Complex molecule + $h\nu \rightarrow$ activated complex. (ii) Activated complex $\rightarrow$ normal complex by spontaneous deactivation of deactivation by collision with solvent molecules.
(iii) Activated complex $\rightarrow$ reduced platinous complex and oxidised organic molecule.

Denoting the concentration of activated complex by c_a and that of the organic molecule *i.e.*, reductant by c_s , we have, under steady condition, *i.e.*, when c_s does not vary,

$$\frac{I_{abs}}{Nh\nu} = k_2c_s + k_3c_a \quad \text{or} \quad c_a = \frac{I_{abs}}{Nh\nu} / (k_2 + k_3)$$

The rate of reaction
$$\frac{dx}{dt} = k_2c_s = \frac{k_2}{k_2 + k_3} \times \frac{I_{abs}}{Nh\nu}$$

i.e., proportional to the amount of light absorbed by the platonic complex.

Now when 366μ is the exciting radiation, it has been observed that the extinction coefficient of the platinous complex is much smaller in comparison to that of the platonic complex, and therefore the velocity of reaction can be written as

$$dx/dt = KI_0(1 - e^{-\lambda(a-x)})$$

where K is the proportionality factor and I_0 , the intensity of incident light. Integrating we get

$$K\lambda I_0 t = \log. \frac{a}{a-x} \cdot \frac{\lambda \cdot x}{2 + \lambda a} \text{ taking the first term in the expansion.}$$

Here λ and I_0 remaining constant, as the amount of substance transformed x will gradually increase, the velocity constant as calculated by $1/t \log a/a-x$ will gradually decrease. This has been actually observed in these experiments.

But when 436μ was the exciting light, though the extinction coefficients of the platonic complex and the platinous complex are smaller in magnitude, they may approximately be taken as equal (*vide* Table VI on extinction coefficient).

$$\text{Here } dl/I = - \left[\frac{\lambda_1(a-x) \cdot dy}{l} + \frac{\lambda_2 x \cdot dy}{l} \right]$$

where l is the thickness of the cell, dy is the region at which the absorbed radiation is to be measured. Allowing stirring at quick intervals, we have taken the average concentration.

$$\text{Hence, } I_{abs} = I_0 \cdot e^{-\frac{\lambda_2 y}{l}} \text{ as } \lambda_1 = \lambda_2 = \lambda \text{ (suppose).}$$

Considering the effective radiation only,

$$\begin{aligned} dx/dt &= K \cdot \int_0^1 I_{abs} \cdot \frac{\lambda \cdot (a-x)}{l} \cdot dy = K \cdot \frac{a-x}{a} \text{ other factors remaining constant.} \\ &= K(a-x) \text{ for each experiment.} \end{aligned}$$

Here in fact concordant unimolecular constants were obtained. The absence of any optical activity with 50% decomposition of the complex in any one of the two kinds of circularly polarised light may be due to spontaneous racemisation of the active variety formed during the process.

*The Photochemical Decomposition of the Complex formed between
Chloroplatinic Acid and Potassium Malonate.*

Determination of the Order of a Reaction.—Here again as in the case of bioxalate with blue light the reactions follow unimolecular course, but in ultraviolet light the unimolecular velocity constants decrease slightly with time. The unimolecular constants record the change for one hour after the induction period is over.

TABLE VII

*Effect of varying the concentration of
chloroplatinic acid.*

λ	Conc. of pot. malonate.	Conc. of chloroplatinic acid.	$I_{abs.}$ *	k_1 .	P/Q .
366 $\mu\mu$	0.07M	0.0133M	4.05 $\times 10^{-10}$	4.72 $\times 10^{-2}$	1.16
	0.06	0.009	3.9	4.24	1.10
436 $\mu\mu$	0.07	0.0133	2.8	0.85	0.30
	0.06	0.009	2.5	0.71	0.284

* $I_{abs.}$ has been presented in Einstein units.

TABLE VIII

*Effect of wave-length of light employed
on quantum yield.*

λ	Conc. of pot. malonate.	Conc. of chloroplatinic acid.	$I_{abs.}$	k_1 .	Quantum efficiency (η)
366 $\mu\mu$	0.07M	0.0133M	4.05 $\times 10^{-10}$	4.72 $\times 10^{-2}$	4.02
436 $\mu\mu$	..	..	4.106	0.86	1.16

As the concentration of chloroplatinic acid is increased, the amount of absorbed radiation and the velocity constant also go on increasing.

TABLE IX

Effect of varying the intensity of absorbed radiation.

Malonate = 0.07M. Chloroplatinic acid = 0.0133M.

$I_{abs.}$ (Einstein $\times 10^{10}$)	0.366 $\mu\mu$		436 $\mu\mu$		
		4.05	2.94	4.11	3.04
Velocity const. ($k_1 \times 10^2$)	4.72	2.92	0.87	0.62	0.51

The rate of reaction is thus proportional to the intensity of absorbed radiation.

TABLE X

Effect of varying the potassium malonate to chloroplatinic acid ratio (= R).

Temp. = 30°.

Malonate.	$\lambda = 366 \mu\mu; I_{abs.} = 3.85 \times 10^{-10}$			$\lambda = 436 \mu\mu; I_{abs.} = 2.65 \times 10^{-10}$		
	R	0.12M	0.06	0.03	0.12	0.06
k_1	3.86 $\times 10^{-2}$	3.84	0.77	0.83	0.82	0.27
η (for first hour)	3.8	3.5	0.65	1.6	1.4	0.3

Up to a limit the variation of concentration of reductant has slight effect upon the velocity of reaction. Beyond this limit the decrease in concentration of the reductant brings about an abrupt drop in the velocity of reaction. The amount of light absorbed remained almost the same in all these cases.

Effect of Polarised Light.—The results obtained were the same as with potassium oxalate. The 50% reduced potassium complex solution, reduced by exposing it to *d*- or *l*-circularly polarised light, was tested for any optical activity with negative result only.

DISCUSSION

The influence of the concentration ratio of potassium malonate/ chloroplatinic acid ($=R$) is interesting in this reaction. When the ratio R is about 3, the quantum yield of the process is about unity. But when R is slightly above 3, quantum yield jumps up to a much higher value and is about 4 when $R=6$, though the absorption of energy does not change.

The reaction is attended with no induction period so long as the ratio R is 3, but with higher values of R induction period suddenly appears and goes on increasing with increasing values of R .

The characteristics mentioned above can be explained in the same manner as in the previous section.

In fact the central feature of this reaction is the peculiar influence of the ratio R on induction period, velocity and quantum yield. These peculiarities can be explained in the following way.

(i) $R=3$. Chloroplatinic acid with three times its concentrations of potassium malonate forms a complex of the type $H_2Pt(M'')_3$, when M'' stands for $H_2C \begin{matrix} \diagup COO^- \\ \diagdown COO^- \end{matrix}$

On exposure to light this complex decomposes according to the scheme :

Here the compound $H_2Pt(M'')_3$ has with E.A.N.*=86, the stable structure of inert radon. Simultaneous release of two electrons by simultaneous detachment of two covalent bonds, due to splitting off of one M'' , establishes a stable structure.

The quantum yield in this case ought to be unity. Experimental evidence supports this expectation.

(ii) $R > 3$. The rate of reaction is entirely different and suggests that some other complex may be involved in the reaction.

For the secondary ionisation constant of malonic acid

$$\frac{[H^-] \times [M'']}{[HM'']} = K, \text{ where } K = 1 \times 10^{-6} \text{ and } HM'' \equiv H_2C \begin{matrix} \diagup COOH \\ \diagdown COO^- \end{matrix}$$

In our reaction mixture H^- concentration = approximately $10^{-4}N$.

$$\text{Hence, } \frac{[M'']}{[HM'']} = 1 \times 10^{-2}$$

* E.A.N. stands for effective atomic number. Atomic number of platinum is 78. Formation of six co-valent bonds with $3M''$ ions results in the sharing of 6 more electrons. Two more electrons are available from two hydrogen atoms. So E.A.N. for $H_2Pt(M'')_3$, is $78+6+2=86$.

When $R=3$, practically all the M' ions are taken up by the complex. So the concentration of HM' is negligible. Hence the chance of formation of any complex of the type $H_2Pt(HM')_6$ is small. When $R > 3$, there is some free M' in the solution and in consequence there must be some HM' ions also. In this case the complex $H_2Pt(HM')_6$ is formed. As the formation of this complex removes free HM' ions from the solution more HM' ions are formed to keep up the equilibrium.

This complex decomposes photochemically according to the scheme:—

- (i) $H_2Pt(HM')_6 + h\nu \rightarrow H_2Pt(HM')_6$ (active).
 (ii) $H_2Pt(HM')_6$ (active) + $H_2Pt(HM')_6 \rightarrow 2H_2Pt(HM')_5 + CO_2$ + other products of oxidation of malonic acid.

The complex $H_2Pt(HM')_5$ is with unstable E.A.N. 55, and is very active because it possesses one lone unshared electron and it takes part in further reactions thus:—

- (iii) $2\{H_2Pt(HM')_5 + H_2Pt(HM')_5\} \rightarrow 4H_2Pt(HM')_4 + 6CO_2$ and other products of oxidation of malonic acid.

The complex $H_2Pt(HM')_4$ with E.A.N. 84, has two unshared electrons which mutually establish a stable structure.

The mechanism indicates a quantum yield of 4. In our experimental results quantum yield of this reaction is nearly 4, when the ratio R is above 3, specially when R is 6.

The sudden appearance of the period of induction when the ratio R is raised slightly above 3, and also its increase with the increase of R , can be explained in a qualitative way on similar considerations assuming that the complex $H_2Pt(HM')_6$ is not formed in the dark. When the reaction mixture is exposed to light, the trimalonate compound, formed in the dark, first of all changes to a complex with higher number of malonate radicals. The time taken for such transformation before the actual photo-decomposition can begin, appears as induction period. Again, the higher the excess malonate present, the higher will be the extent of such transformation. So the induction period will also increase with R .

Here also the absence of any optical activity in the reaction mixture after 50% decomposition under the action of polarised light indicates the possibility of some process of racemisation occurring along with the photo-decomposition.

It must be noted here that the stability of the ring formed between the metallic ion and malonic radical, which is responsible for the existence of asymmetric structure of the complex molecule is much less than the corresponding oxalate compound as evident from the experimental results. This also diminishes the chance of obtaining optical activity in the reaction mixture by favouring racemisation.

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